

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial study of substituted bis-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazine and bis-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidine derivatives

Pradip P. Deohate^{a*} and B. N. Berad^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Shri Radhakisan Laxminarayan Toshniwal College of Science, Akola-444 001, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : pradip222091@yahoo.co.in

^bPostgraduate Department of Chemistry, Shri Shivaji Science College, Amravati-444 603, Maharashtra, India

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Abstract : Series of compounds [4-(3-phenylimino-6-aryl/alkylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinane-4-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(3-phenylimino-6-aryl/alkylimino-[1,2,4,5]-thiadiazinan-4-yl)-methanones and [4-(2-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidine-3-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(2-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-methanones have been synthesized by the interaction of di-(*N*-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido)terephthalamides with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride and *N*-phenyl isocyanodichloride respectively. These compounds on acetylation afforded bis-acetyl derivatives. These compounds have been assayed for their antimicrobial activity against gram-positive as well as gram-negative microorganisms.

Keywords : Bis-dithiadiazine, bis-thiadiazolidine, synthesis, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Synthesis, structural properties and bacteriocidal as well as fungicidal activities of substituted [1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazines¹, [1,4,2,5]-dithiadiazines², [1,4,2,6]-dithiadiazines³, [1,3,4]-thiadiazolidines⁴, [1,2,5]-thiadiazolidines⁵ and [1,2,4]-thiadiazolidines⁶ have been reported earlier in some communications. On perusal of literature, it has been observed that substituted thiadiazolidines have a potential as inhibitors of human leukocyte elastase, cathepsin G. and important for their cytotoxicity⁷. It has been also reported earlier that, substituted [1,2,4]-thiadiazolidines inhibit nuclear transcription factor-kB and its dependent genes activation but induces apoptosis⁶. Synthetic applications of *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride⁸ and *N*-phenyl isocyanodichloride⁹ have been investigated earlier and shown to have enough potentiality in the synthesis of nitrogen and sulphur containing 5 and 6 membered heterocyclic compounds¹⁰. In view of the utility of these reagents in the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds and as a part of wider programme to provide alternative routes of synthesis, now the method for synthesis of substituted bis-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazines and bis-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidines is reported.

Results and discussion

The parent compound terephthalic acid dihydrazide (1) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of terephthalic acid (0.01 mol) and thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) for 30 min, followed by the addition of hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol). It was transformed into di-(*N*-aryl/alkyl thiocarbamido) terephthalamides (3a-h) by condensing with *N*-aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (2a-h) (0.02 mol) in refluxing carbon tetrachloride medium for 2 h by known method¹¹. Compounds (3a-h) were then reacted separately with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride and *N*-phenyl isocyanodichloride in boiling chloroform for 3 h. The evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was clearly noticed as tested with moist blue litmus paper. Cooling the reaction mixture and distilling off chloroform afforded sticky masses, which on washing with petroleum ether gave granular solids. These were acidic to litmus and on titrimetric analysis identified as [4-(3-phenylimino-6-aryl/alkylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinane-4-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(3-phenylimino-6-aryl/alkylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-methanone dihydrochlorides (4a-h) and [4-(2-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidine-3-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(2-phenylimino-5-aryl/alkylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-methanone dihydrochlorides

Note

Scheme 1

(7a-h). These on basification with aqueous ammonia solution afforded free bases (5a-h) and (8a-h) respectively. Compounds (5a-h) and (8a-h) on acylation with acetic anhydride and glacial acetic acid in 1 : 2 ratio yielded bis-acetyl derivatives (6a-h) and (9a-h) (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

The synthesized compounds (5a-h) and (8a-h) were screened for their antibacterial activity using cup plate diffusion method¹². The bacterial organisms used included both gram-positive as well as gram-negative strains like *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis* and *A. aerogenes*. Sensitivity plates were seeded with a bacterial inoculum of 1×10^6 CIU ml⁻¹ and each well (diameter 10 mm) was loaded with 0.1 ml of test compound solution (1000 µg ml⁻¹) in dimethylformamide, so that concentration of each test compound was 100 µg ml⁻¹. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 24 h at 37 °C, using Vernier caliper. Inhibition zone record of the compounds clearly indicated that 5d, 5g and 8d, 8g were highly active against *E. coli*, *B. subtilis* and moderately active against *S. aureus*. Majority of the compounds were found inactive against *S. typhi* and *A. aerogenes*.

To determine minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), the serial dilution technique¹³ was followed using nutrient broth medium. The MIC values of compounds 5d, 5g and 8d, 8g were determined against *E. coli* and *B. subtilis*, which were found to be 65, 70 and 70, 85 µg ml⁻¹ respectively.

Screening of these compounds (5a-h) and (8a-h) having the concentration 1% and 2%, for antifungal activity using paper disc method¹⁴ showed that (5c), (5f) and (8b), (8e) were highly active against *A. niger*, whereas other compounds showed low to moderate activity. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 48 h at 37 °C.

Experimental

The melting points of all synthesized compounds were recorded using hot paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Chemicals used were of A.R. grade. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded with TMS as internal standard using CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ as solvents. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ in nujol mull and as KBr pellete. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel-G plates by TLC.

Parent compound terephthalic acid dihydrazide (1) was

prepared by refluxing the mixture of terephthalic acid (0.01 mol) and thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) for 30 min, followed by the addition of hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) by reported method.

Synthesis of di-(*N*-phenyl thiocarbamido) terephthalamide (3a) :

The compound di-(*N*-phenyl thiocarbamido) terephthalamide (3a) was prepared by refluxing the mixture of terephthalic acid dihydrazide (1) (0.01 mol) and *N*-phenyl isothiocyanate (2a) (0.02 mol) in carbon tetrachloride (20 ml) for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and the solid residue obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (3a) (78%), m.p. 198 °C (Found : C, 56.80; H, 4.31; N, 18.01; S, 13.67. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₀N₆O₂S₂ : C, 56.88; H, 4.34; N, 18.09; S, 13.80%); ν_{\max} 3334, 3328, 3318 (NH), 1708 (C=O), 1289 (C-N), 1236 (C=S), 1210 cm⁻¹ (N-N)¹⁵; δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 8.11 (4H, s, Ar-H), 8.01 (2H, s, CO-NH-N), 6.64–7.40 (10H, m, Ar-H), 4.03 (2H, s, CS-NH-Ar), 2.07 (2H, s, CS-NH-N). This reaction was extended to synthesize other compounds (3b-h) using different *N*-aryl/alkyl isothiocyanates (2b-h) : 3b (80%), m.p. 206 °C; c (68%), m.p. 156 °C; d (76%), m.p. 188 °C; e (82%), m.p. 224 °C; f (75%), m.p. 210 °C; g (85%), m.p. 165 °C; h (79%), m.p. 240 °C.

Synthesis of [4-(3,6-diphenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinane-4-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(3,6-diphenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-methanone (5a) :

Di-(*N*-phenyl thiocarbamido) terephthalamide (3a) (0.01 mol) was suspended in chloroform (15 ml). To this a solution of *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (0.02 mol) in chloroform was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for 3 h. The evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was observed. Then chloroform was distilled off and a sticky mass was obtained. It was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) followed by addition of ethanol, a solid acidic to litmus was isolated, crystallised from ethanol (80%), m.p. 236 °C and identified as [4-(3,6-diphenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinane-4-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(3,6-diphenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-methanone dihydrochloride (4a).

Similarly, other compounds (4b-h) were prepared from (3b-h) : 4b (78%), m.p. 176 °C; c (68%), m.p. 213 °C; d (75%), m.p. 193 °C; e (82%), m.p. 218 °C; f (76%), m.p. 175 °C; g (80%), m.p. 216 °C; h (79%), m.p. 201 °C.

On basification of (4a) with dilute ammonia solution a free base (5a) was obtained, it was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 220 °C (Found : C, 59.11; H, 3.44; N, 15.23; S, 17.52. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{26}N_8O_2S_4$: C, 59.16; H, 3.59; N, 15.33; S, 17.55%); ν_{\max} 3328 (NH), 1697 (C=O), 1590 (C=N), 1310 (C-N), 1228 (N-N), 688 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 8.11 (4H, s, Ar-H), 6.92–7.41 (20H, m, Ar-H), 2.14 (2H, s, NH). Similarly, free base (5b) was prepared from (4b) : 5b, m.p. 168 °C (Found : C, 60.11; H, 3.88; N, 14.70; S, 16.81. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{30}N_8O_2S_4$: C, 60.14; H, 3.98; N, 14.76; S, 16.90%); ν_{\max} 3332 (NH), 1681 (C=O), 1583 (C=N), 1298 (C-N), 1223 (N-N), 693 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 8.09 (4H, s, Ar-H), 6.82–7.08 (18H, m, Ar-H), 2.32 (6H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.14 (2H, s, NH). This reaction was extended to synthesize other free bases (5c-h) : 5c, m.p. 198 °C (Found : C, 60.13; H, 3.88; N, 14.71; S, 16.86. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{30}N_8O_2S_4$: C, 60.14; H, 3.98; N, 14.76; S, 16.90%); d, m.p. 184 °C (Found : C, 60.09; H, 3.84; N, 14.60; S, 16.87. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{30}N_8O_2S_4$: C, 60.14; H, 3.98; N, 14.76; S, 16.90%); e, m.p. 202 °C (Found : C, 54.01; H, 2.8; N, 13.93; S, 15.97. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{24}N_8O_2S_4Cl_2$: C, 54.06; H, 3.02; N, 14.01; S, 16.04%); f, m.p. 168 °C (Found : C, 54.05; H, 3.0; N, 13.94; S, 16.0. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{24}N_8O_2S_4Cl_2$: C, 54.06; H, 3.02; N, 14.01; S, 16.04%); g, m.p. 196 °C (Found : C, 53.93; H, 2.9; N, 13.89; S, 15.99. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{24}N_8O_2S_4Cl_2$: C, 54.06; H, 3.02; N, 14.01; S, 16.04%); h, m.p. 184 °C (Found : C, 55.54; H, 4.83; N, 16.18; S, 18.47. Calcd. for $C_{32}H_{34}N_8O_2S_4$: C, 54.63; H, 4.96; N, 16.22; S, 18.56%).

Synthesis of [4-(3,6-diphenylimino-5-acetyl-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinane-4-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(3,6-diphenylimino-5-acetyl-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-methanone (6a) :

A mixture of [4-(3,6-diphenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinane-4-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(3,6-diphenylimino-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazinan-4-yl)-methanone (5a) (0.01 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in a little crushed ice with water, a whitish solid precipitated was crystallised from warm water with ethanol to give (6a), (81%), m.p. 205 °C (Found : C, 58.89; H, 3.66; N, 13.69; S, 15.69. Calcd. for $C_{40}H_{30}N_8O_4S_4$: C, 58.95; H, 3.71; N, 13.75; S, 15.74%); ν_{\max} 1702, 1688 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1306 (C-N), 1218 (N-N), 691 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 8.11

(4H, s, Ar-H), 6.83–7.51 (20H, m, Ar-H), 2.05 (6H, s, CO-CH₃). This reaction was extended to synthesize other bis-acetyl derivatives (6b-h) : 6b (79%), m.p. 176 °C; c (76%), m.p. 185 °C; d (81%), m.p. 226 °C; e (70%), m.p. 208 °C; f (78%), m.p. 197 °C; g (82%), m.p. 238 °C; h (75%), m.p. 198 °C.

Synthesis of [4-(2,5-diphenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidine-3-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(2,5-diphenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-methanone (8a) :

Di(*N*-phenyl thiocarbamido) terephthalamide (3a) (0.01 mol) was suspended in chloroform (15 ml). To this a solution of *N*-phenyl isocyanodichloride (0.02 mol) in chloroform was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for 2.5 h. The evolution of hydrogen chloride gas was observed. Then chloroform was distilled off and a sticky mass was obtained. It was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), a solid acidic to litmus was isolated, crystallised from ethanol (80%), m.p. 278 °C and identified as [4-(2,5-diphenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidine-3-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(2,5-diphenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-methanone dihydrochloride (7a).

Similarly, other compounds (7b-h) were prepared from (3b-h) : 7b (75%), m.p. 208 °C; c (78%), m.p. 195 °C; d (80%), m.p. 216 °C; e (72%), m.p. 187 °C; f (68%), m.p. 234 °C; g (76%), m.p. 177 °C; h (82%), m.p. 202 °C.

On basification of (7a) with dilute ammonia solution a free base (8a) was obtained, it was crystallised from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 266 °C (Found : C, 64.81; H, 3.85; N, 16.77; S, 9.54. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{26}N_8O_2S_2$: C, 64.85; H, 3.93; N, 16.80; S, 9.62%); ν_{\max} 3357 (NH), 1692 (C=O), 1612 (C=N), 1302 (C-N), 1208 (N-N), 697 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 8.06 (4H, s, Ar-H), 6.81–7.33 (20H, m, Ar-H), 2.12 (2H, s, NH). Similarly, free base (8b) was prepared from (7b) : 8b, m.p. 196 °C (Found : C, 65.65; H, 4.27; N, 16.06; S, 9.21. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{30}N_8O_2S_2$: C, 65.69; H, 4.35; N, 16.13; S, 9.23%); ν_{\max} 3342 (NH), 1684 (C=O), 1601 (C=N), 1289 (C-N), 1219 (N-N), 686 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ (CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 8.01 (4H, s, Ar-H), 6.67–7.03 (18H, m, Ar-H), 2.31 (6H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.12 (2H, s, NH). This reaction was extended to synthesize other free bases (8c-h) : 8c, m.p. 184 °C (Found : C, 65.61; H, 4.30; N, 16.11; S, 9.12. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{30}N_8O_2S_2$: C, 65.69; H, 4.35; N, 16.13; S, 9.23%); d, m.p. 191 °C (Found : C, 65.52; H, 4.19; N, 16.10; S, 9.13. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{30}N_8O_2S_2$:

C, 65.69; H, 4.35; N, 16.13; S, 9.23%); e, m.p. 168 °C (Found : C, 58.71; H, 3.21; N, 15.18; S, 8.66. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{24}N_8O_2S_2Cl_2$: C, 58.78; H, 3.29; N, 15.23; S, 8.72%); f, m.p. 205 °C (Found : C, 58.81; H, 3.18; N, 15.22; S, 8.69. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{24}N_8O_2S_2Cl_2$: C, 58.78; H, 3.29; N, 15.23; S, 8.72%); g, m.p. 161 °C (Found : C, 58.69; H, 3.19; N, 15.17; S, 8.63. Calcd. for $C_{36}H_{24}N_8O_2S_2Cl_2$: C, 58.78; H, 3.29; N, 15.23; S, 8.72%); h, m.p. 186 °C (Found : C, 61.31; H, 5.39; N, 17.83; S, 10.16. Calcd. for $C_{32}H_{34}N_8O_2S_2$: C, 61.32; H, 5.45; N, 17.89; S, 10.23%).

Synthesis of [4-(2,5-diphenylimino-4-acetyl-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidine-3-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(2,5-diphenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-methanone (9a) :

A mixture of [4-(2,5-diphenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidine-3-carbonyl)-phenyl]-(2,5-diphenylimino-[1,3,4]-thiadiazolidin-3-yl)-methanone (**8a**) (0.01 mol) and acetic anhydride (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in a little crushed ice with water, a yellowish white solid precipitated was crystallised from warm water with ethanol to give (**9a**), (78%), m.p. 185 °C (Found : C, 63.81; H, 4.0; N, 14.85; S, 8.47. Calcd. for $C_{40}H_{30}N_8O_4S_2$: C, 63.99; H, 4.03; N, 14.92; S, 8.54%); ν_{max} 1706 (C=O), 1604 (C=N), 1297 (C-N), 1211 (N-N), 697 cm^{-1} (C-S); δ ($CDCl_3$ + $DMSO-d_6$) 8.06 (4H, s, Ar-H), 6.71-7.49 (20H, m, Ar-H), 2.02 (6H, s, CO-CH₃). This reaction was extended to synthesize other bis-acetyl derivatives (**9b-h**) : **9b** (70%), m.p. 165 °C; **c** (76%), m.p. 208 °C; **d** (80%), m.p. 176 °C; **e** (78%), m.p. 210 °C; **f** (82%), m.p. 165 °C; **g** (68%), m.p. 193 °C; **h** (75%), m.p. 189 °C.

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